

The Poultry Industry's Impact on India's Socio-Economic Development

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Abstract

The fastest-growing industry in India is the poultry sector, which offers additional income to the country's impoverished and significant livelihood opportunities. Since it creates income and encourages market investment, poultry is a significant and necessary resource for battling poverty, especially for smallholders and the underprivileged in rural and urban regions. Additionally, the poultry sector significantly contributes to high-quality nutrition and food safety by providing essential macro and micronutrients through the production of meat and eggs, both of which are essential to the development of a healthy society.

Keywords: Poultry, eggs, socio-economic, India

Introduction

The estimated market value of the Indian poultry industry is around Rs. 80,000 crores, and it can be roughly divided into two sub-sectors: one with a highly organized commercial sector that accounts for about 80% of the total market share (roughly Rs. 64,000 crore), and the other with an unorganized sector that accounts for about 20% of the total market share and costs Rs. 16,000 crores (NAPEP, 2022). The unorganized sector, sometimes known as backyard poultry, is essential in assisting the poorest of the poor to produce additional income and fulfil the nutritional and financial needs of their families. Meanwhile, for a variety of reasons, poultry farming can be an effective tool for ensuring food security and a means of subsistence, particularly in developing nations. Additionally, it has enormous potential to grow and improve the accessibility of income sources for many Indian sectors.

Poultry sector contributes significantly to nutrition and food safety by delivering indispensable macro as well as micro nutrients for human being. Due to its quick production cycles and capacity to transform a variety of agro-food by-products and wastes into meat and eggs, it is fit for

building the economy of developing countries. Moreover, poultry is an important and essential resource to reducing poverty, especially for small holders and the poor in rural and urban areas, as it generates revenue and allows for market investment. Particularly in developing nations, poultry is the agricultural subsector with the fastest growth rate. The poultry industry is anticipated to expand globally as demand for meat and eggs is predicted to increase in the future due to rapid urbanization, rising incomes, and explosion of population (Mottet and Tempio, 2017).

The majority of people (65%) in India live in areas where rice or wheat is the main food through which protein intake is quite poor. To prevent protein deficiency and ensure healthy growth, it is crucial to feed these rural and tribal populations nutritious foods with an addition of animal protein. To overcome this, poultry farming is one of the best options as it has a proved ability to reduce poverty, end malnutrition, empower women, offer additional income, and create productive work in rural and tribal regions (Rajkumar *et al.*, 2021). Currently, about 17.8% (18.41 billion) of India's total egg production (103.32 billion) comes from backyard poultry which play an important role in socio-economic development of rural populations (BAHS, 2019). Major objective of poultry production is to supply superior quality animal food/ protein for the growing population that provides a healthy nation with safe food in addition to building the economy of our nation. By considering this objective, present article has mainly designed to know the role, contribution and impediments of poultry sector in socio-economic development of India on sustained basis.

1. Current Indian Scenario on Poultry Farming

India is the world's fourth-largest producer of chicken after China, Brazil, and the USA and the world's third-largest producer of eggs after China and the USA. In India, over the past 25 years, per capita intake of broiler meat has increased from 400 g to 3.8 kg, while that of eggs has increased from 30 eggs to 96 eggs annually (DAHDF, 2019). Even though the production is mainly achieved through commercial means, the rural poultry sector also contributes significantly to the Indian poultry industry. This impressive growth in the poultry sector in general and broiler, layer industry in particular is the result of technological breakthroughs in breeding, feeding, health and sizeable investments from the private as well as government sector (Kumar *et al.*, 2021). The total poultry population in the country is 851.81 million in 2019, increased by 16.8% over previous census. While the total backyard and commercial poultry population in the country is 317.07 million and 534.74 million which is increased by 45.8% and 4.5% over previous census respectively (20th Livestock Census, 2019). Current poultry production scenario in India is compiled in Table.1 and Graph.1

Table 1. Current Poultry Population and Production Scenario in India

Particulars	2012 (In million)	2019 (In million)	Growth(%)	India's Rank in the world
Total Poultry population	729.21	851.81	16.81	6 th
Backyard poultry population	217.49	317.07	45.78	-
Commercial Poultry population	511.72	534.74	4.5	-
Broiler meat production	-	-	11	4 th
Egg production	-	103317	8.51	3 rd

Graph 1. Average Eggs production per year per bird in 2018-19

2. How poultry sector can help to build a healthy nation

Indian poultry farming is one of the most dynamic, techno-commercial, fastest growing, agro-based industry (Sarma *et al.*, 2019). "Socio-economic development" refers to improved living conditions, access to healthy food, and overall health. When people make more money, they spend more on food. Therefore, finding healthy food at a reasonable price will be the main concern which is possible way through poultry farming. Almost all communities accept eggs and chicken, which are also inexpensively available everywhere. Hence, poultry farming is one of the best option and main resource for building a healthy nation as well for the economic development of the nation (Chatterjee and Rajkumar, 2015).

3. Major Impediments of Poultry Industry in India

3.1 More Prevalence Rate of Diseases

Different diseases outbreak has a significant impact on poultry production, including backyard poultry rearing. (Das and Samanta, 2021). India has reported outbreaks of avian influenza (H5N1) in poultry farms every year, where Newcastle disease virus is endemic to India and outbreaks occur every season despite regular vaccination programmes, which causes significant negative economic impact on poultry farming industry (Kumar *et al.*, 2021).

3.2 High Production Cost

Feed expenses account for 65% to 75% of the entire cost of commercial poultry production, and the majority of the components used in poultry feed are imported. Also volatility in feed prices is a serious issue which impedes growth and production by creating uncertainty in the market.

3.3 Poor Marketing Platform

The majority of farmers are unable to take advantage of market prospects in rural areas since markets there are frequently underserved. When markets are readily available, farmers may be subject to price fluctuations or unfair prices.

3.4 Seasonal factors

The poultry industry faces a variety of fresh difficulties at the start of each new season. Birds are prone to heat stress in the summer, which adds extra costs like air conditioners and increased ventilation that increase power usage. Also, birds consume less feed due to summer stress, which can sometimes lead to feeding wastage or higher FCR (Biswal *et al.*, 2022). The monsoon's arrival brings another problem like the quantity and quality of feeding are both impacted by the humidity and temperature drop.

4. Advices for Strengthening Indian Poultry Farming

- It is advised that the poultry farming market be regulated in terms of product pricing due to the current issues encountered during the pandemic.
- During any disease outbreaks, stable policy guidelines and proper awareness should be provided for consumer trust.
- In order to manage the sustenance of poultry farms and provide a minimum standard operating environment and safety to monitor the poultry workers' health, a regulatory authority should be established.
- The competent authority must do a random inspection at the farm site while the license is being granted or before the loan is sanctioned.
- The market needs well defined areas, and open meat sales should be avoided.

Conclusion

Despite the difficulties encountered over the years, India's poultry production has continued to increase in a spectacular manner. With rising demand for chicken meat and eggs, Indian poultry industry is expected to continue to grow and commercialization. The nutritional and economic conditions of people in rural areas will improve with the adoption of small-scale chicken farming in the backyards of rural households which plays a significant role in socio-economic development of India. Future obstacles won't be a barrier due to the advancement of knowledge and new findings in all aspects of poultry, which looks promising for the future of poultry production that helps to build up a healthy nation.

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